

Milestone: MS34 Detecting innovation opportunities

Lead Participant: BSC

Author: Carles Hernandez-Ferrer

Due: 31 July 2025

Date Of Completion: 31 October 2025

Means of Verification

Participation and presentation at the **ELIXIR Bioinformatics Industry Forum (EBIF) 2025**, showcasing our work on federated processing within **GDI** and **EUCAIM**. The presentation https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1dMj1g-icfhiQO0S9v3_5w4GZGJHneqB6lZqnCba3gcg/edit?usp=sharing highlighted how these initiatives open opportunities for industry engagement and co-development of future European standards in federated data analysis.

Milestone Delayed (if yes, please explain)

—

Project participants & others

Activity led by Carles Hernandez-Ferrer (deputy lead of WP8), with contributions from GDI and EUCAIM partners. Engaged with ELIXIR industry and research stakeholders, including representatives from academia, biotech, and health data infrastructures, fostering dialogue on innovation needs and collaboration models.

Next action steps

- Collect and analyze feedback from industry participants at EIF 2025.
- Identify specific innovation opportunities and partnership pathways emerging from the forum.
- Prepare a follow-up roadmap to align GDI's federated processing developments with European interoperability and industry standards.

